

AGROECOseqC

AGROECOLOGICAL strategies for an efficient functioning
of plant - soil biota interactions to increase SOC
sequestration

Handbook

(WP1-WP6)

Sampling and analytical protocols

WP1

AGROECOseqC OBJECTIVE

AGROECOseqC multifunctional approach starts from the hypothesis that, by introducing agroecological management practices based on plant diversification and reduced soil disturbance, the plant community shapes soil microbial community involved C-nutrient cycling, this improving the overall microbial CUE and capacity to store C in soil. The expected higher synchrony between plant nutrient demand and soil nutrient availability under agroecological practice will also increase the stable SOC pools, reduce N-leaching and mitigate GHG emission, contemporary boosting those beneficial plant-microbe interactions able to increase biomass production and crop yield.

By recognizing agroecosystem biodiversity and plant-soil interactions as main drivers of soil C and nutrient fluxes, the AGROECOseqC will study the ability of diversified agroecosystems to store SOC using a multifunctional system approach. Plant and soil biota community structure, plant and microbial metabolic activity, soil nutrient fluxes, and SOC sequestration will be measured in two periods of the year:

- at plant growth when soil functions as C source (MAX nutrient uptake)
- at dormant plant when soil functions as C sink (MIN nutrient uptake)

The obtained results will be incorporated in multivariate analyses and models of C and N fluxes to understand the mechanisms underlying plant-soil interactions and their regulating role on carbon and nutrient cycling.

AGROECOseqC experimental sites include mostly long-term experiments (LTE) and two recently established ones. The selected sites are representative of two crossed gradients of ecological intensification: i) a local-scale gradient and ii) a European-scale gradient built in the frame of this project.

AGROECOseqC CORE SITES (CS) DESCRIPTION

CODE	Name of partner	Name of the experiment	Site location (country, city, GPS coordinates)	Pedoclimatic Region	Mean annual temperature (°C)	Mean annual rainfall (mm y-1)	Year of experiment set up	Products	Type of plants	Plant perennality	Applied diversification
CS1	CREA	MAIOR LTE	Italy, Rome, N 41,7989529 E 12,5721093; altitude 86 m a.s.l.	Hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa, Köppen classification),	15,7 °C average value of month means (May 2016 -April 2021)	750,4 mm average value of month means (May 2016 - April 2021)	2017	Organic apricots	Trees & Herbaceous	Perennials & annuals	Cover crop / soil tillage
CS2	INRAE-Clermont Ferrand	NSC (New cropping systems)	France, Clermont Ferrand, 45°46'27.03"N 3°8'31.02"E; altitude 339 m a.s.l.	Temperate with relatively cold winters and hot summers, continental influences	12,75°C average value calculated for the period 2016-2020	514 mm average value calculated for the period 2016-2020	September 2016	Forage, wheat grains and straw	Herbaceous plants	Perennials & annuals	Mixture of Spring wheat with a diversified perennial herbaceous
CS3	INRAE-Montpellier	DIAMS (Instrumented Agroforestry site under Mediterranean Climate)	France, Mauguio, 43°36'45.3"N 3°58'37.7"E; altitude 13.6 m a.s.l.	Hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa, Köppen classification)	15,6°C average value of day means (December 2016 - December 2021)	740 mm average cumulated by year	2017	Cereals and legumes	Trees and herbaceous strips under the tree line,	Perennials and annuals	Agroforestry
CS4	AU	GrassTools/GrainLegsGo labeling experiment	Denmark, Foulum, 56° 30' N, 9° 34' E, altitude 45 m a.s.l.	Oceanic climate (Cfb, Köppen classification)	°C (mean 2015-20	749 mm (2015-2018)	2021	Cereal & grain legume grains, grass biomass	Herbaceous	Perennials & annuals	Intercropping in space and time
CS5	INIA-CSIC	LTE La Canaleja	Spain, Alcalá de Henares, 40.5233807 N, -3.1241509 600m asl	Hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa, Köppen classification)	14.3°C	389	1994	Wheat	Cereals	Annuals	Rotation vs monoculture in Standard/Minimum/Zero tillage
CS6	WUR	Clever Crop Experiment	Netherlands, Wageningen, 51° 59' 41.9" N, 5° 39' 17.5" E	Marine West Coast Climate	9.1	895	2016	Cereal and maize grain, silage maize	Herbaceous	Annuals	Cover crop
CS7	LAMMC	"Extensive soil tillage and cover crop influence on soil quality and productivity of phytocenosis"	Lithuania, Akademija, Kedainiai distr., N 55,39722222; E 23,86111111	Nemoral	6.5	592	2013	Cereal grains	Herbaceous	Annuals	Cover crop and no-tillage
CS8	TAGEM	New Experiment	Turkey, Sanliurfa; 36°53'12.72"N - 38°55'15.04"E	Anatolian	18.50	463.30	New experiment	Tomatoes	Herbaceous	Annuals	Cover crop and fungi inoculation
CS9	CRAW	LTE-OM	Belgium, Gembloux, Latitude = 50.5606556, Longitude = 4.7264556, Altitude = 170 m	Zone environnementale (Metzger et al., 2005) : "Atlantic central" (ATC)	10,4 °C	730 mm/year	1959	Arable crops. 3 years rotation : sugar beet, winter wheat and winter barley	Arable crops	Annual	Diverse organic matter management:

More details about the CSs are reported in the file "AGROECOseqC core sites description.xlsx".

AGROECOseqC SAMPLING PLAN

Number of samples and sampling times

1. In all the 9 core-sites: 3 treatments x 4 blocks x 1 replicates/block = **108 soil samples**. Each sample will be a composite sample from 4 sub-samples collected within each plot (protocols will report details of sampling mode).
2. To evaluate agricultural practice considering the spatial variability, **in only in 3 core-sites** (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC) will be collected **36 soil samples**: 2 treatments x 3 block x 2 replicates (1 replicates already sampled as 1 replicate/block) = additional 12 soil samples per each core-site

TOTAL: 108 + 36 = 144 soil samples

Sampling plan per each WP and measurement

WP	Measurement/indicators	SAMPLING PLAN		ADDITIONAL SAMPLES		TOTAL
		Number of total samples 9 core-sites, 4 replicates (1 per block), 3 treatments	Number of samplings/year (1/2)	To assess the practices: in 3 core sites: 12 additional samples per site (CREA, LAMMC, CSIC-INIA)	Number of samplings / year (1/2)	
WP2	Weed coverage/density (species-specific); weed biomass; cover crop biomass	108 x 2 (min uptake only when plants in field)	2 (max and min)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	252
WP2	Root mycorrhizal colonization intensity	108	1 (max)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	144
WP2	Soil mineral N, soil available P.	108 x 2	2 (max and min)	-		216
WP2	Plant N, P content (marketable yield and residues)	108	1 (at harvest)	-	1	108
WP2	P-solubilizing root fungi	108	1 (max)	-	1	-
WP3	Macrofauna (only on CS1, CS3, CS5, CS6, CS9)	60	1 / 2	-	-	max 120
WP3	Mesofauna	108	1	-	-	108

WP3	Microfauna	108	1	-	-	108
WP4	DNA sequencing analysis of bacteria and fungi (NGS)	108	1 (max)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	144
WP4	Microbial community-level physiological profiling analysis	120	1 (max) only on 2 treatments	-	-	120
WP4	Functional genes involved in SOM accumulation (q/dPCR) (only on 5 cores-sites)	60	1 (min)	-	-	60
WP4	Soil biomass C (SMB-C)	108	1 (max)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	-	144
WP5	Estimation of plant nutrient demand	120 (INRAE Clermont-Ferrand, AU, CREA, BOKU, ..)	T0 -> T1	-	-	-
WP5	Labelling with ¹³ C-CO ₂ (only on 5 cores-sites)	60 (AU, LLAMC, INRAE-Clermont-Ferrand, CREA, BOKU)	1 (end of labeling period)	-	-	60
WP6	Soil aggregates stability SOC and MAOC on soil micro- and macroaggregates	108	1 (max)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	144
WP6	SEM-EDS semi-quantitative C/P analysis of soil aggregates	108	1 (max)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	144
WP6	dsDNA	108 x 2	2 (max and min)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	252
WP6	Soil enzymatic activity	108 x 2	2 (max and min)	36 (CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)	1	252
WP6	SOM decomposition tests	max 108	1 (lab test)	-	-	108

IMPORTANT: ADDITIONAL PARAMETERS TO BE DETERMINED - As additional mandatory measurements, the **bulk density** and the **total organic carbon (TOC)** must be determined by each partner in their experimental site on each plot, to apply ROTH-C model and MVA. In each core site: 3 treatments x 4 replicates = 12 plots to be analysed per TOC and bulk density.

Since most variables will be measured on sieved soil at 2 mm, we will refer to **density of fine soil** (sieved soil at 2 mm).

When sieving soils, the **>2 mm coarser fraction or gravel** must be collected and weighted to calculate the **soil bulk density** when running the multivariate analysis.

Soil total organic carbon (**TOC**) must be determined by **dry combustion methods** (as C/N/S Analyzer).

Soil sampling for TOC and bulk density should be carried out in correspondence of the other soil sampling, anyway not after soil tillage.

OPTIONAL: Please, collect data or determine the soil texture in each plot at each CS (13 treatments x 4 blocks = 12).

Legenda:

- MAX = soil sampling at peak of green biomass (maximum nutrient uptake, when soil functions as C source)
- MIN = sampling at minimum nutrient uptake by the plant (when soil functions as C sink).
- The two sampling moments (MAX and MIN) can vary in function of each cropping systems.
- The sampling campaign will start in each CS in late summer- early autumn 2022 (MIN).
- Sampling MAX in each CS will be from November 2022 to July 2023.
- Collection of all samples will end in summer 2023.
- Determination and data evaluation should be concluded not later than July 2024.

DESCRIPTION OF SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Number of plots - In AGROECOseqC, in each core-site, three selected agronomic practices (treatments) will be tested in four blocks (field replicates) for a total of 12 plots (3 treatments x 4 replicates = 12). **Each “plot” represents the field unit of each treatment in each block.**

All partners involved will collect soil/plant/root samples for WP2/3/4/5/6 activity within the **12 identified plots**. Only CREA, LAMMC and CSIC will collect 12 additional samples (2 treatments x 3 replicates) to apply MVA on agronomic practices.

Plant and soil biota community structure, plant and microbial metabolic activity, soil nutrient fluxes, and SOC sequestration will be measured in two periods of the year:

- at plant growth when soil functions as C source (MAX nutrient uptake)
- at dormant plant when soil functions as C sink (MIN nutrient uptake)

as reported in "Sampling plan" table (pages 5-6).

NB: N, P content of plant biomass (marketable yield and plant residues, WP2) must be determined at harvest, by each partner.

GANNT CHART

WP5 activity - Only WP5 activity will involve the set of green sub-plots (**A** and **B**) to estimate the biomass accumulation during the period T0->T1 (see: WP5 – Estimation of plant nutrient demand).

All the other soil/plant/root samples will be collected into the sub-plot **C** at MAX and/or MIN nutrient demand, as reported in sampling plan (pages 5-6).

ATTENTION! Each partner must identify in **both the MIN and the MAX uptake periods** the two sampling moments **T0** and **T1** for WP5 determination and carry out the following sampling:

- At T0, plant biomass should be collected and weighted from unfertilized A sub-plots (if present, as fresh and dry weight).
- At T0, the B sub-plots must be fertilized (see Figure 1).
- At T1 (at max 4 weeks after fertilization), plant biomass should be collected from fertilized B sub-plots and weighted (fresh and dry weight).
- At T1 (after max 4 weeks) plant biomass should ALSO be collected from not-fertilized C sub-plots and weighted (fresh and dry weight) and soil samples collected from C sub-plots and sent to all partners.

That means that 1) the sampling procedure above described has to be repeated two times, at MAX and MIN plant uptake (see GANNT chart), and 2) the purpose of WP5 requires to collect biomass (subplots A) and fertilize plant covers (subplots B) several weeks before the soil sampling

Sampling protocol

After dividing each sub-plot **A**, **B**, **C** into 4 quadrats (with a side of min. 0.5 m - max. 2.0 m, see figure above reported), 4 soil sub-samples will be collected, then mixed to form one composite sample.

In A and B sub-plots, only the sampling related to estimation of plant nutrient demand (WP5) will be performed (see detailed description at WP5 section).

All the other soil / plant / root / fauna samples will be collected in sub-plot C, by sampling n.4 elementary sample in each quadrat to form a single composite sample per plot.

At **CREA**, **LAMMC** and **CSIC**, on 2 treatments and in 3 blocks, 3 sub-samples per each plot will be maintained separated to evaluate agronomic practices by MVA.

Treatments, replicates & studied plots / site

- **3 treatments:**
 - control treatment (a «business as usual» practice)
 - 1st improved «agroecological» practice
 - 2nd improved «agroecological» practice (in some cases, it corresponds to the combination of the 1st agroecological practice with another practice (es. no tillage + crop diversification) -> gradient of ecological intensification)
- **4 replicates /treatment**
- Total number of studied plots /core-site: $3 \times 4 = 12$

AGROECOseqC sampling plan

At **INRAE, WUR, AU, CRAW, TAGEM** core-sites, all the tested parameters will be evaluated on 12 samples per each sampling moment (MIN/MAX), following the sampling plan reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Graphical synthesis on how to collect sub-samples and form the composite ones by **INRAE (n.2 core-sites), WUR, AU, CRAW, TAGEM** partners.

AGROECOseqC sampling for agronomic practices evaluation (sub-task 7.1.2).

Only at **CREA, CSIC-INIA and LAMMC** core-sites, the effect of agronomic practices on diversity of plant, soil fauna and soil microbial community affecting C sequestration will be evaluated by multivariate analysis (Sub-Task 7.1.2). For this purpose, it was decided to collect 3 sub-samples per each block to consider the spatial variability and to correlate soil chemical, physical and biological parameters to plant diversity in field.

Thus, the following the sampling plan was proposed, where:

- on 2 treatments and 3 blocks, n. 3 sub-samples/block will be collected and maintained separated
- in parallel, on 3 treatments and 4 blocks, n. 4 composite samples will be formed by mixing the 3 sub-samples.

In Figure 3, the sampling plan at CREA, INIA-CSIC and LAMMC core-sites is described.

Figure 3. Graphical synthesis on how to collect sub-samples and form the composite ones at CREA, INIA-CSIC and LAMMC.

CREA, CSIC-INIA and LAMMC will manage a total of **24 samples**: [(3replicates x 3 blocks) + 1 composite (Bl 4) x 2 treatments] + 4 blocks x 3rd treatment = 10 x 2 + 4 = 24 samples. Elementary samples will be maintained separated (36) or averaged as composite samples and sent to partners referring to the table “Sampling plan per each WP and measurement” table at page 4.

This choice will allow to:

- apply multivariate analysis (Sub-task 7.1.2) with an adequate numbers of replicates per treatments (3 blocks x 3 sub-samples = 9 replicates; 9 replicates x 2 treatments = 18 elementary samples)
- consider only n. 1 composite sample/block/treatment (by mixing the n. 3 elementary samples) to be used for all the other WPs activity (es. modeling actions).

Note: To make coherent the statistical evaluation of composite samples from all the partners (3 treatments x 4 blocks = **12 samples**), considering the high number of replicates per treatment collected at CREA, CSIC-INIA and LAMMC, all composite samples will be formed by mixing 3 sub-samples, instead of 4 sub-samples.

The soil layer studied in AGROECOseqC is 0-20 cm. This means most measurements will be carried out on soil sampled within this soil layer.

Root sampling will be performed on 0-30 cm layer.

Soil/plant/root sampling will be carried out according to the WPs protocols.

Regarding the two sampling moments, corresponding to MAX or MIN plant nutrient demand, they could differ in different core-sites, depending on pedo-climatic conditions and cover crop species. We assume as minimum plant demand (MIN) the moment in which the soil functions as C-sink (before ploughing in the early-late autumn, before cover crops sowing), while maximum plant demand (MAX) when the soil functions as C-source (in the late spring/early summer, at cover crop full flowering stage, just before termination).

Sample type, amount, storage, and shipping

Measurements at MIN uptake period

- **T0**: Plant biomass (if present) collected in the four quadrats in **A sub-plot**, to obtain a composite plant sample (WP5, all plant biomass present in field)-> data to INRAE, Clermont-Ferrand, France).
- **T0**: Fertilization of B sub-plot.
- **T1**: Plant biomass collected in the four quadrats in **fertilized B and in unfertilized C** sub-plots to obtain a composite plant sample (WP5, all plant biomass present in field)-> data to INRAE, Clermont-Ferrand, France).

At **T1**: all the other measurements described below:

- Soil nutrient supply (WP5, 150 g of 0-20 cm fresh, sieved soil at 2 mm, sent at max 5°C, **shipped on ice packs** a.s.a.p., not later than 48 hours from sampling) -> INRAE, Clermont-Ferrand, France).
- Weed coverage/density (species-specific); weed biomass; cash crop/cover crop biomass (WP2, data set) -> CREA AA Rome, Italy. *If no plant species are found in field, it can be escaped.
- Soil mineral N, soil available P (WP2, 200 g of fresh 0-20 cm soil, shipped within max 48 hrs) -> TAGEM, Turkey
- Macrofauna (only on CS1, CS3, CS5, CS6, CS9) (WP3 -> to be sampled at each site), only if appropriate, based on pedo-climatic conditions. Otherwise, this sampling must be carried out at MAX plant demand -> INIA
- Functional genes involved in SOM accumulation (WP4, 50 g of 0-20 cm fresh soil, sieved at 2 mm stored at -20°C and **shipped on dry ice**) -> CREA

AA Bologna, Italy). *Sending will be postponed in function of the number of CSs where this measurement will be applied: in this case, samples must be stored at -20°C.

- dsDNA and soil enzymatic activity (WP4/WP6, 100 g of fresh 0-20 cm soil, **shipped on ice pack** -> CREA VE, Conegliano, Italy).

Measurements at MAX uptake period

- **T0**: Plant biomass (if present) collected in the four quadrats in **A sub-plot**, to obtain a composite plant sample (WP5, all plant biomass present in field)→ data to INRAE, Clemond-Ferrand, France).
- **T0**: Fertilization of B sub-plot.
- **T1**: Plant biomass collected in the four quadrats in **fertilized B and in unfertilized C** sub-plots to obtain a composite plant sample (WP5, all plant biomass present in field)→ data to INRAE, Clemond-Ferrand, France).

At **T1**: all the other measurements described below:

- Soil nutrient supply (WP5, 150 g of 0-20 cm fresh, sieved soil at 2 mm, sent at max 5°C, **shipped on ice packs** a.s.a.p., not later than 48 hours from sampling) -> INRAE, Clemond-Ferrand, France).
- Weed coverage/density (species-specific); weed biomass; cover crop biomass (WP2, data set → CREA AA Rome, Italy) in unfertilized plots (C)
- Root mycorrhizal colonization intensity (WP2, washed roots collected at 0-30 cm depth, shipped within max 24 hrs, refrigerated (4°C, **on ice packs**) -> CREA AA Rome, Italy)
- SEM analysis of mycorrhizal network in soil aggregates (WP2, 50 g of fresh 0-20 cm undisturbed soil, shipped within max 24 hrs, refrigerated (4°C, **on ice packs**) -> CREA AA Rome, Italy)
- Soil mineral N, soil available P (WP2, 200 g of fresh 0-20 cm soil, shipped within max 48 hrs → TAGEM, Turkey)
- Plant N, P content (marketable yield and residues, **at harvest**) (WP2, 100 gr dried plant residues/marketable → TAGEM, Turkey or by each countries)
- P-solubilizing root fungi (WP2, roots collected in field with wet soil covered, shipped refrigerated (4°C, **on ice packs**)→ TAGEM, Turkey)
- Macrofauna (only on CS1, CS3, CS5, CS6, CS9) (WP3, to be sampled at each site)
- Mesofauna (WP3, 100g at 0-10 cm depth and 10 cm wide soil → INIA, Spain)
- Microfauna (WP3, 100g at 0-15 cm depth → INIA, Spain)

- DNA sequencing analysis of bacteria and fungi (NGS) (WP4, 200 g of 0-20 cm fresh soil, sieved at 2 mm, stored at -20 °C, and **shipped on dry ice** → CEBAS-CSIC, Spain)
- Microbial community-level physiological profiling analysis (only on 2 treatments) (WP4, 200g of 0-20 cm fresh soil, sieved at 2 mm → LAMMC, Lithuania, and IIAG-CSIC, Spain)
- Soil biomass C (WP4, 200g of 0-20 cm fresh soil → LAMMC, Lithuania)
- dsDNA and soil enzymatic activity (WP4/WP6, 100 g of fresh 0-20 cm soil, shipped **on ice packs** → CREA VE, Conegliano, Italy).
- Labelling test with ¹³C-CO₂ (only in AU, LLAMC, INRAE-Clemont-Ferrand, CREA, BOKU) (WP5, 100 g of fresh topsoil **on ice** → AU, Denmark) (see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eifer5j03_0)
- Soil aggregates stability, SOC and MAOC on soil micro- and macroaggregates (WP6, 1 kg of 0-20 cm undisturbed soil at field capacity → LAMMC, Lithuania)
- SEM-EDS semi-quantitative C/P analysis of soil aggregates (WP6, 50 g of separated micro- and macroaggregates to be sent from LAMMC → CREA AA Rome, Italy)
- SOM decomposition test (WP6, 100 g of 0-20 cm soil refrigerated (sent at max 5°C, **on ice packs**) → CREA VE, Conegliano, Italy)

Schemes for soil/biomass/root sampling

Soil sampling will be collected with respect to row spacing, applicable also for broadcast seeding. In case of agroforestry, plots will be set at fixed distance from the tree rows, to guarantee the simultaneous presence of roots of the tree crop (if present in the upper soil layer), the cover crop and wild spontaneous flora/weeds.

In figure below, the sampling of plant biomass, bulk soil, and root systems in different cropping systems considered in AGROECOseqC is graphically represented, in function of:

- the cropping system (herbaceous crop: row-by-row or broadcast);
- the block (field replicate) area (<5m² and >5 m²).

Herbaceous crop (row-by-row) - Block area <math>< 5m^2</math>

Herbaceous crop (row-by-row) - Block area >math>> 5m^2</math>

Grass cover (broadcast) - Block area <math>< 5m^2</math>

Grass cover (broadcast) - Block area >math>> 5m^2</math>

AGROFORESTRY

AGROFORESTRY

Important - The sampling points can be selected in the rows or in-between the rows, depending on the crop, the cropping system, and the plant distance within the rows. Anyway, **soil, plant biomass and root sampling must be carried out where plant diversity is the highest.**

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Sample coding at shipping

Alphanumeric code will be generated as follows:

- **INRAE, AU, WUR, TAGEM, CRAW** : 1, 2, 3, 4,, 12 = sequential numbers
- **CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC**: 1, 2, 3, 4, ..., 24 = sequential numbers

CS1, CS2, CS3, .. = CS numbering, as reported in the core-site description sheet (see page 3)

S, P, R = matrix (Soil, Plant, Root)

Min / Max = Min uptake/Max uptake

T1, T2, T3 = treatments per each CS (agroecological intensification: T1 <T2; T3 = control)

B1, B2, B3, B4 = block number

A, B, C = replicate per block (only in CREA, CSIC-INIA, LAMMC)

Example: **n.11 (CS1.S.Min.T2.B3.A)**

Core site 1 (CREA), soil sample, min uptake, treatment 2, block 3,
replicate B)

WP2

DRIVER 1: PLANT COMMUNITIES AND RHIZOSPHERE PLANT-MICROBE INTERACTIONS

Objective

Understanding the role played by plant diversity and functional traits on microbial beneficial interactions (mycorrhizal symbiosis, rhizobia, Trichoderma, etc.) and their effect on plant nutrient uptake and yield

T2.1: Plant functional diversity and effect on soil C inputs and retention

Elena Testani, Corrado Ciaccia (CREA)

Parameters:

- percentage of coverage or density (depending on the cover development) of each spontaneous flora species

Methodology:

- When: at MAX and MIN plant uptake
- What: cover crop % of coverage (or density); weed % of each species coverage (or density); cover crop and weed biomass for C-input assessment. If at MIN sampling no plant species will be in field, the sampling can be skipped.
- How: in field, phytosociological survey at species level will be performed in 1 m x 1 m sampling quadrat (in case of coverage assessment) or less (eg, 0.25 m x 0.25 m, depending by the plot size and if species density is determined). In each quadrat the weed species should be identified. Each component (weed species and ASC species) will be counted (density) or their per cent cover (coverage) estimated, and the number registered in a

previously prepared species/sample matrix. In case of cover crop mix, individuals by each species should be registered. For weeds, the number of individuals per species is desired to calculate diversity indices.

In the same sampling quadrat, after phytosociological survey, cover crop and weeds aboveground biomass will be measured in 0.25 m x 0.25 m, by clipping all plant material at ground level. The samples will be dried (separating cover crop and weeds) for 48 h at 70 °C, to determine their dry matter weight and then stored for following analysis of C concentration (g kg^{-1}) using the method usually chosen in the lab (e.g., elemental analysis by dry combustion method).

Quadrat choice: 1 m² for coverage; smaller for density

Density assessment

Coverage assessment

- Replicates*: to obtain each replicate, we recommend averaging the species coverage (or density) values from at least 4 quadrats (in the same area where to collect the cylinders for mycorrhiza and the soil samples to be mixed to obtain the composite sample).

*In the same quadrats, a composite soil sample should be averaged and then sent to WP4 and WP6 for further analysis.

Only at CREA, CSIC-INIA and LAMMC core sites, additional two soil composite replicates will be supplied to test agronomic practices (to obtain 3 replicates x 3 block x 2 treatments).

Indicators:

- Diversity indices of spontaneous plant community (i.e., H, R or E, R);

From trait analysis (by calculating the Community-level Weighted Mean (CWM) of the weed traits of interest, which measures the weighted average of traits for the species pool in the weed community):

- SAM (supporting arbuscular mycorrhization) species % (or SAM/no SAM species ratio)
- Perennial %, or Perennials/Annuals ratio;
- C4/C3 ratio;
- N Ellenberg value (low and high range of values);
- Growth rate related traits (e.g., SLA, seed weight)

T2.2: Fungi mycelial network development influencing soil aggregates formation

Alessandra Trinchera (CREA), Skaidre Suproniene - LAMMC

Parameters

- mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%) of representative plant species (crop + cover crops + main spontaneous species)
- presence (YES/NO) of mycorrhizal external hyphae in soil micro- and macro-aggregates

Methodology

Root sampling in field - To quantify the root mycorrhizal colonization intensity (M%) of relevant plant species in field (i.e., service crops, as cover crops or intercropped crops), their root apparatus (cask crop + cover crops + spontaneous flora) must be collected by using stainless steel cylinders of 6 cm diameter and 30 cm length (sampled soil layer, below organic layer: 0-25 cm, Trinchera et al., 2016).

Per each treatment, four root sub-samples must be collected to form one global root sample per each block. The four root samples should be collected within the four quadrats considered for plant diversity evaluation (T2.1).

Hereafter a short video showing plant root sampling in field:

[Handbook Root sampling in field](#)

Collected roots must be immediately separated from the bulk soil by washing with tap water at room temperature on a sieve of 0.5 mm mesh, to obtain a total of 1 plants' root composite sample x 3 treatments x 4 blocks = **12 per each core site**. **Only in CREA, LAMMC and CSIC, additional 12 soil samples** per each core-site should be collected (2 treatments x 3 block x 2 replicates/block, being 1 replicate sampled as 1 replicate/block).

Each root sample must be transferred in a plastic tube (volume about 50-200 mL, depending on the amount of collected roots), adding an amount of tap water to ensure root wetting. Important: be sure that all the roots are completely covered by water. **IMPORTANT:** Do not use distilled water to wash or maintain the roots: it can cause root collapse.

Within 24 hrs. after root collection, tubes containing roots in water must be sent to CREA AA (Rome) refrigerated at 4°C for further analysis.

Determination of mycorrhizal colonization intensity of sampled roots -

Collected roots will be ordinated into first, second and third-order lateral roots. At random, from each root sample, a total of 10×1 cm root fragments per plant (third-order lateral roots, diameter 1.0÷2.0 mm) will be cut from 5 mm to 15 mm from the root tip by a razor blade. The root fragments will be stained by a solution of 0.05% w/v methyl blue in lacto-glycerol (1:1:1 lactic acid, glycerol and water) for 1 minute and destained by distilled water for 1 minute more (Grace and Stribely, 1991). Then, the root fragments will be placed on grinded slides, mounted in a drop of glycerol, and observed under a light microscope. The

mycorrhizal colonization intensity of each root sample will be assessed by applying the method of Trouvelot et al. (1986), based on the observation on of the root fragments occupied by AMF structures. For each “i” plant species and treatment, the total number of observed fragments was: 3 plants x 3 blocks x 10 = 90. Mi% was calculated attributing to each root fragment increasing scores from 0 to 5: 0 = no AMF structures within the root segment; 1 = structures occupy less than 1% of the root segment; 2 = structures occupy less than 10% of the root segment; 3 = structures occupy less than 50% of the root segment; 4 = structures occupy more than 50% of the root segment; 5 = structures occupy more than 90% of the root segment. The Mi (as %) for each “i” plant species was calculated as follows:

$$M_i = (95n_5 + 70n_4 + 30n_3 + 5n_2 + n_1) / \text{total number of observed fragments}$$

where n₅ is the number of fragments rated 5, n₄ is the number of fragments rated 4, and so on. M% is expressed as percentage of covered roots by AMF structures.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of extraradical hyphae on mycorrhizal roots – The objective of roots inspection by SEM allow to verify the presence of hyphal network into soil aggregates of different average dimension. This is the reason we need to collect them without any physical disturbance.

In the same quadrat of phytosociological survey and plant root sampling, from a carefully diged hole of 0-20 cm depth using a flat shovel an undisturbed soil sample must be taken at adequate moisture (normally moist – moisture close to field capacity). Transfer the soil sample portion (100 gr minimum) into closed, clean glass/plastic bottles or plastic envelopes [if using bottles, please fill completely or add blotting paper into the upper empty space to avoid the disruption of soil aggregates during transport (see an example in picture below)]. NB: Take care to not destroy the soil aggregation. Per each CS, 3 treatment x 4 replicates = 12 soil samples.

The soil must be sent to CREA at temperature of 4°C for following microscopic analysis. On those samples, Scanning Electron Microscope (Microscope Zeiss - EVO MA10) under variable pressure equipped with a LaB6 (SEM-BSE) will be applied to evaluate the presence/amount of mycorrhizal external mycelial network. The applied variable pressure mode (at 20-25kV EHT/20-10 Pa chamber pressure) prevented surface damages of such biological and non-conductive samples, giving a high-resolution image without any prior sample preparation.

Scanning Electron Microscope ZEISS EVO MA10

- Electron source: LaB₆
- Mode: Variable pressure (chamber pressure: 20 Pa)
- Detector: VPSE
- EHT: 20.00 kV

This samples will be evaluated without previous separation of aggregates: SEM analysis will allow to associate to the aggregates of different dimensions (to be evaluated during the Scanning Electron Microscopy analysis) the presence/absence of mycorrhizal hyphae (see figure below reported).

Undisturbed soil observed by SEM-VP (LaB6 Electron source)

Indicators:

- Quantitative indicator of agroecosystem mycorrhization (MA%, Trinchera et al., 2019; 2021)
- Presence/absence of external mycorrhizal hyphae in soil micro- and macro-aggregates (scores: from 0 to 3).

T2.3: Plant-microbe beneficial symbioses and effect on crop N-P uptake

Akin Un (TAGEM)

Objective:

Evaluate the cascade of agroecological management on effect crop N-P uptake through rhizosphere beneficial symbiosis.

Composite soil samples will be collected in each block/replicate for each treatment and at least 200 g of soil must be sent to TAGEM (to the attention of Akin Un).

Parameters:

- microbial-solubilized P in soil solution by symbiotic microorganism
- soil available P and N (at maximum/minimum crop uptake needs)
- P - N content in marketable yield and/or plant residues, depending on the cropping system

Methodology:

- Pikovskaya Agar environment (Pikovskaya et al., 1948) will be used to analyse Solvent Effect of Phosphorus. Each involved partner can send root samples covered by soil-to TAGEM if not available for indoor analysis.
- At the stages of maximum/minimum plant uptake (MIN, MAX), soil available P and N content will be determined in soil samples taken from 0-20 cm depth. The soil available (extractable) P content will be determined by the Olsen method (Olsen et al., 1954), using as extracting solution: 0.5 M sodium hydrocarbonate solution to reach pH 8.5. NOTE: High pH soils give lower Olsen P levels, whereas low pH soils will yield higher Olsen P levels, often over-estimating the soil P status. In high pH soil, Melich III method can be applied, using as extracting solution: 0.2 M acetic acid + 0.015 M ammonium fluoride + 0.013 M nitric acid + 0.25 M ammonium nitrate + 0.001M EDTA). Obtained extracts are analyzed by simultaneous plasma emission spectrophotometer (ICP-OES, $\lambda = 720 \text{ nm}$).
- Soil Mineral N (SMN, $\text{NO}_3^- \text{-N} + \text{NH}_4^+ \text{-N}$) extracted by 2 M KCl (1:10, w/v) and measured by continual flow colorimetry according to Krom (1980) and Henriksen and Selmer-Olsen (1970) for $\text{NH}_4^+ \text{-N}$ $\text{NO}_3^- \text{-N}$, respectively, or using alternative methods available in lab.

At harvest, P and N content in marketable yield and/or crop residues will be analysed.

The N content of the plant samples will be determined using combustion method (-> C-N Analyser).

Phosphorus content of plant samples will be determined after dry mineralization (incineration) of 5 g at 400°C per 24 hrs (Campbell and Plank, 1998). Obtained ashes are re-solubilized by adding HNO_3 20%, transferred in a 25 mL flask, brought to volume and then analysed by ICP-OES.

Indicators:

- pH corresponding to optimal soil fungi and/or bacteria P solubilizing effect

- Δ avN-P in soil
- Plant N-P uptake

Soil Samples

- 1- Should be sent as soon as possible. If not, they should be stored in a refrigerator between 0-4 °C for a couple days (about 2 days)
- 2- Samples should be sent in a bags or cartons.
- 3- Transfer should be fast shipping, not longer than 2 days from EU to Turkey.
- 4- Weigh at least 500 g of each distributed sample.

Plant Samples

- 1- If soil samples will be sent directly, it is better to send them fresh, in perforated envelopes
- 2- If the sending will be postponed, it can be dried in the lab.

Pikovkaya Method

Pikovskaya is a nutrient medium used to determine the Phosphorus Solvent effect of microorganisms forming colonies in the soil and especially on the root. This method will be applied to evaluate the ability of beneficial symbiosis to solubilize P in soil and increase P uptake by plant. The rationale is to test i) spontaneous beneficial symbiosis or ii) addition of microbial inoculants (e.g., selected fungi species).

Partners can send sample in two ways:

- a) roots collected in field with wet soil covered can be sent to TAGEM, or
- b) isolated or selected fungi samples can be sent directly to TAGEM.

Samples Time

Soil samples will be collected and sent at seeding/planting time or before applying fertilizer and harvesting time or just before harvesting time.

The plant and its fruit (when possible) samples will be collected in field at harvesting time for N and P analysis. Due to constraints in shipping plant samples to TAGEM, partners may analyze N-P content by themselves.

For analyzing “Microbial-solubilized P in soil solution”, roots covered with soil samples should be sent as soon as possible at +4 °C. They can be sent with dry ice. In 5 days after removing from field, the sample must be started to prepare for analysis. Also, partners can send us microbial fertilizer directly.

If fungi samples are sent immediately, the analysis takes about 10 days.

If roots with wet soil are sent immediately, the analysis takes about 1 months.

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WP3

SOIL MACRO- MESO- AND MICROFAUNA FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY

Objective

Studying the composition of the soil food web, including all relevant faunal groups, to identify taxonomical and functional characteristics of soil fauna and quantify its contribution to C sequestration.

T3.1: Soil microfauna functional diversity

Sara Sánchez-Moreno, Joaquín Cobos

Parameters:

- Soil nematode fauna composition to genera/family level

Methodology:

- Soil samples will be collected at the maximum nutrient demand period (MAX) at all the experiments. At each plot, subsamples of 100g aprox. will be collected with a soil corer or spade at 0-20 cm depth. Subsamples will be gently composed and homogenized to form a single 300g composite samples will be analyzed from each plot (108 samples in total).
- Un-sieved soil samples will be immediately shipped with ice blocks to the Soil and Nematode Ecology laboratory at the INIA-CSIC. From each sample, 25 g will be used to measure soil moisture by drying at 70°C. 200g will be used to extract all nematodes through Baermann funnels. Once extracted, all nematodes will be counted under a binocular microscope Leica M80 and 100 nematodes will be identified to genus/family level in a light microscope Leica DM2500 equipped with a differential interference contrast system.
- Once identified, all nematodes will be classified according to trophic group (Yeates et al., 1993) and colonizer-persister group (Bongers, 1990). Maturity

indices (Bongers, 1990), soil food web indices (Ferris et al., 2001) and nematode metabolic footprints (Ferris, 2010) will be calculated using the NINJA online tool (Sieriebriennikov et al., 2014).

Indicators:

- Taxa richness.
- Nematode abundance and biomass.
- Maturity index (MI), Maturity index 2-5 (MI2-5), Enrichment Index, Structure Index, Channel Index, Basal Index, and Nematode Metabolic Footprints.

References:

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2014.02.004>.

T3.2: Soil mesofauna functional diversity

Jordi Moya Laraño, Sara Sánchez-Moreno

Parameters:

- Soil mesofauna composition to species level.

Methodology:

- Soil samples will be collected at the maximum nutrient demand period (MAX) at all the experiments. At each plot, 1 intact subsample will be taken with a soil corer 10 cm deep and 10 cm wide. Depending on soil properties, sample weight will be aprox. 1000g.
- Samples will be kept in plastic container of adequate size and shape to maintain the soil core intact and will be immediately shipped with ice blocks to the Soil and Nematode Ecology laboratory at the INIA-CSIC. All samples will be processed immediately after arrival.
- Mesofauna will be extracted from all samples with Berlesse funnels (Krantz and Walter, 2009). Once extracted, all individuals will be identified under a binocular microscope Leica M80, and, when necessary, individuals will be fixed and mounted in permanent slides to complete the identification under the microscope.

Indicators:

- Taxa richness. Faunal list for different groups of soil organisms.
- Abundances of mites, collembolans, and arthropods.
- Ecological indices, including alpha and beta diversity indices and indicators of similarity across sites and experimental treatments.

References:

Krantz and Walter (eds), 2009. A manual of acarology. Texas Tech. University Press. Lubbock, Texas, 807 pp.

Figure: [sampling for micro and mesofauna](#)

T3.3: Soil macrofauna functional diversity I: Earthworms.

Juan José Jiménez, Sara Sánchez-Moreno

Parameters:

- Soil macrofauna composition to species level (Oligochaeta).

Methodology:

- Soil samples will be collected at the maximum nutrient demand period (MAX), although specific sampling dates may vary depending on climatological conditions. Only those sampling sites with large plots will be sampled. Since soil macrofauna move very actively, only sites with a minimum plot surface will be sampled (CS1 (CREA), CS3 (INRAE), CS5 (INIA), CS6 (CRA-W), and CS9 (WUR)).
- Earthworm sampling will be performed through hand-sorting. Vegetation will be cut at the sampling spot without standing on it, and a simple wire or wooden frame (25 cm x 25 cm) will be put on soil surface. If there is a litter layer, it will be transferred onto a plastic tray and earthworms and any other clearly visible macrofauna will be hand-sorted. Then, a 25 cm x 25 cm x 25 cm deep will be excavated and put on the plastic sheet or tray, and earthworms and other fauna will be sorted manually. Individuals will be washed in clean water and kept in 96% ethanol. To achieve an adequate fixation and to avoid organism's damage, change completely the ethanol after a few hours. Samples will be sent to JJ Jiménez (IPE-CSIC) for analyses.

Indicators:

- Taxa richness. Faunal list for different groups of soil organisms.

- Abundances and biomass of earthworms and other soil macrofauna.
- Ecological indices, including alpha and beta diversity indices and indicators of similarity across sites and experimental treatments.

References:

J.J. Jiménez, J. Filser (Eds.), and the KEYSOM Team, 2020. Soil fauna: key to soil organic matter dynamics and modelling. HANDBOOK OF METHODS. COST Action ES1406.

Figure: [sampling for macrofauna \(earthworms\)](#)

T3.4: Soil macrofauna diversity II: arthropods

Joaquín Cobos Sabate, Sara Sánchez-Moreno,

Parameters:

- Taxonomical and functional diversity of arthropods.

Methodology:

- Arthropods will be sampled in certain core sites (to determine) depending on plot size, agronomical practices and financial limitations. At each selected site, pitfall traps will be used to collect soil arthropods. Individuals will be kept in ethanol 70° and identified. Sampling will be performed by the EBD-CSIC team, which will travel to selected CSs for sampling. The diversity of the arthropod community across management options will be analyzed. All analyses will be performed in R software (R Core team, 2020).

Indicators:

- Taxonomical and functional diversity of arthropods and relation to between arthropod diversity, soil C storage and soil management.

Figure: [sampling for micro](#) and [mesofauna](#)

Pitfall traps (2.5 cm Ø, 5 cm deep, 70 % ethanol - 30 % [monoethylene glycol](#)). Number of pitfall traps per CS variable.

Pitfall traps active for 96 hours (warm and sunny days, end of spring).

Sampling protocol optimization in Coria del Rio, Seville Spain

T3.5: Identification of key attributes of soil food web structure which drive c cycling

Sara Sánchez-Moreno, Joaquín Cobos Sabate

Parameters:

- Statistical models describing the relationships between soil biodiversity, soil functioning, C sequestration, and agricultural management.

Methodology:

- Data on soil properties will be obtained from other WP (texture, C, N, P, mineral N, pH, electrical conductivity). The information on soil diversity obtained from previous tasks, will be analyzed together with the data on soil properties and experimental treatments. Different statistical analyses will be performed, including linear and non-linear models and multivariate ordination analyses. All analyses will be performed in R software (R Core team, 2020).

Indicators:

- Statistical relations between soil diversity, soil C storage and soil management.

References:

R Core Team (2020). R: a language and environment for statistical computing. R foundation for statistical computing, Vienna, Austria.

WP4

SOIL MICROBIAL FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY

Objective:

Elucidate specific microbial species adaptation and their function distribution within the context of different pedoclimatic conditions, agricultural management, demand of plant nutrients and increase and persistence of soil organic carbon.

Task 4.1 Soil microbial functional diversity: Identification of the major drivers of C cycle to use them as indicators of C use efficiency

Protocol of methodologies Subtask 4.1.1 and Subtask 4.1.2

Subtask 4.1.1 Agroecological practices effect on microbial soil communities

Margarita Ros and José Antonio Pascual (CEBAS-CSIC)

Soil sampling

Fresh soil must be sieved by 2 mm, calculate soil moisture and store at -20 °C and shipping on dry ice for DNA extraction. Ten grams per sample.

Soil DNA extraction

Soil DNA will be extracted from 0.5 g of soil using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro kit (Qiagen, Germany) extraction kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's instructions.

The quantity of the DNA will be calculated by a Qubit 3.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), and the quality will be measured by NanoDrop (UV spectroscopy).

DNA should have a good quality, it means

$A_{260}/A_{280} > 1.7$

$A_{260}/A_{230} > 1.8$ and yields $> 12 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{l}$

Soil DNA will be stored at -20°C until sequencing on an Illumina MiSeq platform.

DNA sequencing analysis

The library preparation will include sample quality control and Nextera two-step PCR amplification using primer sets 341F/805R or 515F/806R (V4 region of 16S rDNA) and ITS3/ITS4 or gITS7/ITS4 (ITS2 or ITS4 Region of the ITS rDNA), PCR product purification, quantification and equimolar pooling. The DNA for Microbial Community Analysis samples $> 5 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{l}$ per sample. Sequencing on Illumina MiSeq, v3, 2 x 300 bp. Demultiplexing and trimming of Illumina adaptor residuals and trimming of locus specific primer sequences.

Bioinformatic analysis

Raw sequence data generated from Illumina Miseq will be processed in QIIME2 v 2020.2.0 (Caporaso et al., 2010) through Oracle Virtualbox v 6.1. Fastq files were imported into QIIME2 with the 'single end method' and the sequences will then denoised and filtered with the dada2 pipeline to remove noisy and chimeric sequences (Callahan et al., 2016). The reads will be clustered into exact amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). The ASVs obtained were taxonomically classified against the SILVA 132 and UNITE database QIIME2 v 2020.2.0 developer release using a scikit-learn naive Bayes machine-learning classifier ('q2-fit-classifier-naive-bayes' and 'q2-classify-sklearn' plugin) applying the 'precision' configuration to maximize classification precision as proposed by Bokulich et al. (2018).

Functional analysis is done by PICRUSt2 v2 for 16S rRNA and FunGuild for ITS genes with R version 4.0. To study carbohydrates Active Enzyme CAZy programme is used.

Different diversity indexes are analyzed Shannon index, Hill2 index or number of OTUs. Different tools as MANOVA, PERMANOVA, PCAs etc., according to the approach required will be analyzed by [Team R Core \(2019\)](#).

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Callahan, B.J., Mc Murdie, P.J., Rosen, M.J., Han, A.W., Johnson, A.J.A., Holmes, S.P., 2016. DADA2: high-resolution sample inference from Illumina amplicon data. *Nat. Methods* 13, 581–583.

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Subtask 4.1.2 Identification of functional genes as indicators of C use efficiency

Luisa Maria Manici, Ludovica Saccà, (CREA)

This subtask will focus on the identification of soil fungi functional genes involved in C sequestration.

Due to the high analytical and bioinformatic costs, this activity will be preliminary tested on different soils (not AGROECOseqC core-sites), and in 2023 applied in a given numbers of AGROECOseqC core-sites. Anyway, we suggest collecting soil by all partners, to be ready to send it.

The soil sampling will be carried out at the moment of MIN plant demand, by collecting soil at 0-20 cm depth. Soil should be air-dried, sieved at 2 mm and stored at -20°C for DNA analysis.

50 g of 0-20 cm dried soil (filling at least 30 mL of a 50 mL test tube) should be sent under on ice at -20°C to CREA AA – Bologna (Italy) to the attention of Luisa Manici & Ludovica Saccà.

Quantification of Ascomycetes, Basidiomycetes and total fungi

Total genomic DNA will be extracted from 0.25 g of bulk soil (dry weight) using the PowerSoil DNA Isolation kit according to manufacturer instructions (Qiagen). Quantification and quality control of DNA will be performed using Infinite 200 NanoQuant (Trading AG, Switzerland) and DNA will be stored at -20 °C until use. Ascomycetes, Basidiomycetes and total fungi will be quantified from bulk soil DNA by real-time PCR (qPCR) using the following primers: ITS1F/ITS4A, ITS1F/ITS4B and ITS1F/ITS4 respectively. Standard curves for quantification of unknown samples will be obtained by using 10-fold serially diluted purified amplicons of fungal reference strains (Bustin et al., 2009). The gene copy number will be calculated with the following formula: $\text{gene copy}/\mu\text{L} = \text{DNA (ng}/\mu\text{L)} \times 6.02 \times 10^{23} / \text{base pairs} \times 660 \times 109$. qPCR assays will be carried out using QuantStudio 3 Real-Time PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Three technical replicates will be performed for each sample and sterile water will be used as no-template control in each run. Briefly, 1x PowerTrack SYBR Green Master Mix will be used in a final reaction volume of 10 μL , with a final primer concentration of 0.4 μM and 0.5 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$ of DNA. After an initial PCR activation step at 50 °C for 2 minutes and 95 °C for 2 minutes, cycling conditions consist in 1 second denaturation at 95 °C, and 40 cycles of combined annealing extension at 60 °C for 30 seconds. Results will be analyzed with the Quantstudio™ Design & Analysis Software, Version 2.6 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Quantity will be expressed as number of gene copies/ μL .

Identification of fungal genes of functional interest in carbon cycle and SOM quality and quantification with Digital PCR

Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)

The DNA extracted from bulk soil will be used for identifying fungal populations (ITS2) through amplicon sequencing using Illumina technology (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Libraries will be constructed following Illumina Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation protocol in two amplification steps: an initial PCR amplification using locus-specific PCR primers and a subsequent amplification that integrates relevant flow-cell binding domains and unique indices (NexteraXT Index Kit). For the first PCR step, ITS3_KYO2 forward primer

GATGAAGAACGYAGYRAA (Toju et al. 2012) and ITS4r reverse primer TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC (White et al 1990) will be used for the amplification of the ITS2 fungal rDNA region. The amplicons will be sequenced on Illumina MiSeq 2x 300 bp paired-end platform (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA, USA).

Quantification of target functional genes by Digital PCR

Based on the results from NGS analysis of fungal populations in bulk soil, digital PCR (dPCR) assays will be designed for the absolute quantification of target functional genes selected, selected after a preliminary screening on a set of soils differently managed (apart from AGROECOseqC core-sites).. dPCR will be used for its great precision and sensitivity (Huggett, 2020). DNA samples will be diluted for dPCR analysis so that the concentration of target sequence in the final reaction is in the optimal range of 200-2000 copies/ μ L. A QuantStudio™ 3D Digital PCR System (Thermo Fisher Scientific) will be used following manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 1x Custom TaqMan Assay was used in a final reaction volume of 15 μ L, with 1x QuantStudio 3D Digital PCR Master Mix v2 and 2 ng/ μ L of DNA. Samples are loaded into the wells of a QuantStudio™ 3D Digital PCR 20K Chip v2 using a QuantStudio™ 3D Digital PCR Chip Loader and placed in a ProFlex™ 2 × Flat PCR System for thermal cycling. Cycling conditions consist in 10 minutes denaturation at 96 °C, and 40 cycles of combined annealing extension at 60 °C for 2 minutes and 98°C for 30 seconds. Following thermal cycling, chips will be imaged with a QuantStudio™ 3D Digital PCR Instrument. Results will be analyzed with the QuantStudio® 3D AnalysisSuite™ software version 3.1.6-PRC-build18. Two technical replicates of chips containing identical sample/assay/reaction mix combinations and volumes will be performed. No-target controls and no-template controls will be included in the assay. Results will be expressed as copies of DNA target/ μ L.

References

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TASK 4.2. Effect of agroecological practices on microbial biomass and activity

4.2.1. Protocol of methodologies of Task 4.2

Soil sampling

Soil samples should be collected in sub-plots C, by sampling 4 0.20 cm sub-samples per each sub-plot, then collected to form one composite soil sample/plot. Soil must be sieved by 2mm, calculate soil moisture and store at 4 °C and shipping on dry ice for analysis. (35-40 grams), to evaluate the main soil enzymatic activities.

Enzyme activities related to C, N and P

Flavio Fornasier (CREA VE)
Melania Migliore (CREA AA)

Per each replicate: 30 g of fresh soil

Number of samples: 4 replicates per plot >> sample all plots

All of the potential enzymatic activities are measured in duplicate from all the soil samples by a heteromolecular exchange procedure (Fornasier and Margon, 2007). Briefly, 0.4 g of soil (fw) place into 2-mL microcentrifuge tubes, together with 1.4 mL of a solution containing 3% lysozyme and glass beads. The tubes are then subjected to bead-beating using a Retsch 400 beating mill at 30 strokes s^{-1} for 3 min, followed by centrifugation at 20,000 g for 5 min. The supernatant containing desorbed enzymes is dispensed into 384-well white microplates with the appropriate buffer to fluorometrically quantify the enzymatic activities. (i) C-cycle: β -glucosidase (gluc), acetate esterase (ester); iii) P-cycle: acid (acP)- and alkaline phosphomonoesterases (alkP), pyrophosphate-phosphodiesterase (piroP); and (iv) S-cycle: arylsulphatase (aryS) using fluorescent, 4-methyl-umbelliferyl- (MUF), and (ii) N-cycle: chitinase (chit), leucine-aminopeptidase (leu) using 4-amido-7-methyl-coumarine (AMC).

All measurements are done in duplicate and the activities are expressed as nanomoles of MUF (or AMC) $\text{min}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$ dry soil.

Indirect quantification of C-stock in living woody deciduous species (biomass) and in deadwood considering the different components and decay classes

Living wood

In each sampling plot, the main dendrometric data—such as height and diameter at breast height (dbh) for all standing living trees, number of stems, canopy cover overstorey—are collected during the field measurements. The standing living (stem) volume was estimated using the model elaborated by second Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) for black pine species (Tabacchi et al., 2011). In this model, the diameter at breast height (d) and the total tree height (h) are adopted as independent variables for the prediction equations.

Deadwood

Three deadwood components are considered and measured in the sampling plot: (1) lying deadwood or logs (sound and rotting pieces of wood located on the ground); (2) snag (standing dead trees with a height greater than 1.3 m); and (3) stumps (standing dead trees truncated or cut to a height of less than 1.3 m). Considering size of deadwood, threshold diameter for distinguishing between

deadwood and litter is set up: all woody debris with a diameter greater than the fixed threshold (commonly from 4 to 8 cm) are recorded and classified, while the woody debris with a diameter less than fixed threshold are considered as litter. In each plot, lying deadwood is sampled using two sampling methods: fixed-area sampling (FAS) and line intersect sampling (LIS). (De Meo et al. 2017)

References

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Microbial community-level physiological profiling analysis (CLPPs)

Carmen Trasar-Cepeda, Serafin González-Prieto and Ángeles Prieto-Fernández (IIAG-CSIC), Renata Žvirauskienė, Skaidrė Supronienė (LAMMC)

CLPPs will be performed on soil samples collected at the moment of maximum plant uptake (see table of “Sampling plan – pages 5-6).

This analysis will be managed by both IIAG-CSC and LLAMC. In particular:

- IIAG-CSIC: CS1, CS5, CS6, CS9 total 48 samples (+12 CS7, as internal control) = 60 samples
- LAMMC: CS2, CS3, CS4, CS7, CS8 total 60

Microbial community-level physiological profiles are determined using Biolog EcoPlates™ (Biolog Inc., Hayward, CA) containing 31 different carbon sources, plus a water control.

10 g of soil samples is suspended in 90 ml sterile 0.85% NaCl solution. The soil is shaken in suspension for up to 1 hour in an orbital shaker and then left to stand for 30 minutes. The dilutions (ratio 1:100) are made to inoculate Ecoplates with 100 µl in each well. Colour development (optical density, OD) has to be determined by reading absorbance every 24 hours for 4 days at 26 °C using a Microstation (MicroLog MSystem, Biolog Inc.) at a wavelength of 590 nm. The data are collected using Microlog Data Collection Software 1.2 (Biolog Inc.) / (PowerWave XS2, BioTek Instruments, USA).

Calculations and data analysis

Plate readings after 48 hours of incubation are used to calculate AWCD, microbial Richness (R) and Shannon diversity index (H). After subtracting the absorbance of the control well for each substrate and setting all negative readings to zero to normalise data.

AWCD values are determined according to the formula: $AWCD = \Sigma(C - S)/31$ (Garland and Mills, 1991) where C is scale value of the control well (without a carbon source) and S is scale value of the sole carbon source of each of the 31 sources. R values are calculated as the number of utilised carbon substrates with $OD > 0.25$. H is calculated according to the formula: $H = -\Sigma p_i (\ln p_i)$, where p_i is the relative value between the absorption value and the sum of all positive wells. H separates the physiological diversity of microbes according to the technology specificity. AWCD, R, and H are analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and mean comparisons between treatments are performed using Tukey's mean separation test. The smallest significant difference R_{05} is calculated using a probability level of $P < 0.05$. Where required, repeated measures analysis are used to test for changing effects over time.

Carbon substrates are divided into six groups according to Chazarenc et al. (2010). The normalised (subtracting the control well value and negative values set to zero) OD readings of each series are averaged.

References

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Chazarenc F., Brisson J., Merlin G. 2010. Seasonal and Spatial Changes of Microorganism Communities in Constructed Wetlands: A Community Level Physiological Profiling Analysis. *Int. J. Chem. Eng.* 10, 490240

Soil biomass carbon (SMB-C)

Flavio Fornasier (CREA) and Modupe Doyeni (LAMMC)

SMB-C was calculated from the differences in extractable organic carbon (OC) between the fumigated and non-fumigated soil samples with a conversion factor (K_{EC}) of 0.38.

SMB-C was calculated as

$$SMB-C = E_c / K_{EC}$$

where $E_c = (\text{OC extracted from fumigated soil}) - (\text{OC extracted from non-fumigated soil})$ and $K_{EC} = 0.38$.

Soil microbial biomass carbon fumigation-extraction method (Vance et al., 1987). Twenty g of soil measured and fumigated via exposing the soil to the alcohol-free chloroform (CHCl_3) vapor in a sealed vacuum desiccator for 24 h. The fumigated soil evacuated repeatedly in a clean empty desiccator until the odor of CHCl_3 is no more detected and then extracted with 80 ml of 0.5M K_2SO_4 (soil: $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 = 1:4$) for 30 min by oscillating shaking at 200 rpm and then filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The fumigated extracts are stored at a temperature of 4 °C prior to further analysis (dichromate digestion).

Organic carbon content in the extracts is then determined using the dichromate digestion method. Two ml of potassium dichromate ($\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (66.7mM) and 15 ml of the digestion mixture (2:1 conc. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$ (vol/vol) is added to 8 ml of extract in a 250 ml conical flask. The mixture is gently refluxed for 30 min, allowed to cool and diluted with 20 ml distilled water. The excess $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ was measured by titration with ferrous ammonium sulfate (40.0 mM) using a 1.10-phenanthroline-ferrous sulfate complex (25 mM) solution as an indicator.

References

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WP5

LEVEL OF SYNCHRONY BETWEEN PLANT NUTRIENT DEMAND, SOIL NUTRIENT FLUXES AND SOIL ORGANIC MATTER DYNAMICS

Objectives

The specific objectives of this WP are to:

- Plant nutrient demand: Quantifying the demand in nutrient of plant covers during two contrasting moments in terms of plant growth
- Nutrient supply by soil biota: Evaluating the impact of agricultural practices on the supply of mineral nutrients by soil biota and its response to time (periods)
- Soils as sink and source of carbon and nutrients: Determining the capacity of soils to act as sink and/or source of carbon and nutrients under the different agricultural practices
- Level of demand/supply synchrony: Determining the level of synchrony between plant nutrient demand, soil nutrient fluxes and soil organic matter dynamic.

Only the three first objectives require experimental measurements. The last objective will be assessed by statistical and modelling approaches.

Methods

Sebastien Fontaine (INRAE) and Jim Rasmussen (AU)

1. Estimation of plant nutrient demand

This estimation concerns all experimental sites and will be conducted at two contrasting moments, characterized by highest and lowest plant nutrient demand, that need to be defined for each site depending on their local conditions.

Definition of plant demand: it corresponds to the amount of nutrients needed to convert the photosynthesis-derived carbon in biomass. The plant demand is a potential that is not necessarily satisfied by the soil offer of soluble nutrients.

General approach: the plant's nutrient demand will be calculated from 1) the plant net photosynthesis under non-limited conditions of nutrients (need to fertilize with NPK) and 2) the critical nutrient content of plant growth specific to plant species (values taken in literature). Plant N demand = net photosynthesis x critical nutrient content.

Figure WP5.1. Principle sketch for estimating net plant photosynthesis involving two biomass sampling times and two fertilization levels (the standard and a subplot with optimal/unlimiting nutrient supply). By standard we mean the fertilization level (+ nutrient supply by the soil) that is already included in the studied practices/treatment.

Method to estimate net plant photosynthesis (NPP). NPP is quantified from the difference in aboveground biomass C measured between two times (T0 and T1, Figure WP5.1) that need to be defined according to local agricultural systems and moments of measurement (Min or Max plant nutrient demand). It is important to well distinguish these two times (T0 and T1) during which NPP will be measured from the two moments chosen to characterize two status of plant-soil functioning (Min and Max plant nutrient demand). The aboveground biomass C will be measured using quadrat approach (Figure WP5.2)

Definition of sampling times T0 & T1 for measuring NPP

T1 -> main sampling date during which plant biomass will be harvested to estimate biomass accumulation and plant N demand, but also during which all other measurements and sampling will be done (measurement of plant diversity, sampling of root, soil, etc.).

T0 -> pre-biomass-accumulation time (several weeks before T1). This time must be defined depending on local agricultural systems and period of measurement (Min or Max plant N demand). The duration between T0 and T1 must be sufficient to detect a significant increase in aboveground plant biomass, but not too long since the plant N demand measured during the period T0->T1 will be compared to the soil offer measured at T1.

Fertilisation treatment at T0. In order to satisfy the non-limited condition of nutrient availability during biomass accumulation, the plant cover sampled at T1

(set of green quadrat in the middle, Figure WP5.2) must be fertilized with mineral NPK at T0. The amount of nutrients applied must be estimated from the need of plant species at the moment of measurement (the classical fertilization plan can be applied)

Figure WP5.2 General description of protocols to set up in field for the estimations of plant nutrient demand and soil nutrient supply. The set of green quadrats at left is used to estimate the plant biomass at the beginning of the biomass accumulation period (aboveground biomass cut at T0). The set of green quadrats in the middle is used to estimate the biomass accumulation during the period T0->T1 (aboveground biomass cut at T1). This set of quadrats must be all fertilized at T0, after biomass cut. The set of brown quadrats at right will be used to perform all the other measurements (plant diversity...) and samplings (soil, roots...) at times T1. There will be two times T1 corresponding to the two periods of measurements (Min and Max plant N demand)

2. Quantification of soil nitrogen supply and carbon use efficiency

2.1 Soil sampling and shipping

The four independent soil samples taken within the quadrats (set of brown quadrats at right, Figure WP5.2) must be sieved at 2mm and homogenized to produce 1 composite sample per plot. If the soil is too wet to be sieved, let it dry on a plateau at room temperature for 1-2 hours to facilitate the sieving. A subsample of 160g of soil must be taken from the composite sample using the method of quartering. The fresh sieved soil must be sent with ice packs to maintain a temperature $<5^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the travelling (avoid direct contact of soil with ice). The shipping must be done as soon as possible using a fast-shipping mode.

Send the soil samples to Sebastien Fontaine (INRAE, UREP, 5 chemin de Beaulieu, 63000 Clermont Ferrand, FRANCE)

2.2 Soil nitrogen supply.

The soil nitrogen supply is determined by two opposed soil nitrogen fluxes generated by soil microbes, the N mineralization and immobilization. These two fluxes are quantified using the ^{15}N pool dilution technique (Davidson et al., 1991; Recous et al., 1995; Mary et al., 1998).

Soil incubation: 100 g (dry weight basis) of fresh soil is sprayed with a solution (3 ml) composed of ^{15}N labelled NH_4Cl ($\delta^{15}\text{N} = 2500\%$) and KNO_3 . The solution is prepared in order to bring an equivalent of $30\text{mg N-NH}_4 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ soil and $13.3\text{mg N-NO}_3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ soil. The soil moisture is initially adjusted to reach a water potential of -100kPa after the addition of labelled N solution. Soil is mixed to homogenize the labeled solution in the soil. Two sets of incubated flasks are prepared from ^{15}N labelled soils. For each set, an aliquot of 30 g (dry weight basis) of soil is transferred in glass bottles (100 ml) closed with a rubber septum. A first set is sampled after for 2 hours (T+2h) and the second one after 26 hours of incubations (T+26h).

Content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of mineral N: Soil inorganic N content (N-NH_4^+ and N-NO_3^-) is measured before and after the addition of labeled N at T0 and T1. Inorganic N content is extracted in tubes with KCl 2M (62.5 mL of solution in 25g of dried soil). Tubes are shaken during 30 minutes at 300 rpm and then centrifuged at $3000 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$ for 5 min. Extracts are filtered (0.45 mm) and analyzed. For the ^{15}N measurements, NH_4^+ and NO_3^- are separated by distillation with MgO and Dewarda's alloy. To this purpose, the excess of KCl extraction solution is transferred into closed bottle diffusion traps in the presence of either MgO or Dewarda's alloy and NH_4^+ and NO_3^- are collected using acidified filter paper disks. Inorganic ^{15}N is measured using an isotope-ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS; EA; Carlo Erba, Rodana, Italy).

Content and delta ¹⁵N of soil organic nitrogen: following the mineral N extraction with KCl, soils are washed with water in order to eliminate more than 99% of the residual KCl and mineral N. For the washing, the aliquot of 30 g of soil is shaken with 140 ml water during 30 seconds. The water is removed after centrifugation. The procedure is repeated 3 times. Soils are dried at 60°C for 24h and grounded. Organic N and its isotopic composition are determined using an isotope-ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS; EA; Carlo Erba, Rodana, Italy).

Calculation of N fluxes: We determine gross N mineralization (m) (mg N kg soil⁻¹ 24h⁻¹) and immobilization (i) rate (mg N kg soil⁻¹ 24h⁻¹) by using the following equations (Davidson et al., 1991; Mary et al., 1998):

$$m = \frac{M_0 - M_1}{t} \times \frac{\log\left(\frac{H_0 \times M_1}{H_1 \times M_0}\right)}{\log\left(\frac{M_0}{M_1}\right)} \quad (7)$$

Where M₀ is the initial ¹⁴⁺¹⁵NH₄ pool (T+2h) mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil), M₁ is the post incubation (T+26h) ¹⁴⁺¹⁵NH₄ pool (mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil), H₀ is the initial (T+2h) ¹⁵NH₄ pool (mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil), H₁ is the post incubation (T+26h) ¹⁵NH₄ pool (mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil) and t is the time of soil incubation (24 hours). The gross N immobilization rate is calculated by using a constant rate called k and the difference of organic ¹⁵N content between initial and post incubation content (mg N kg⁻¹ dry soil) called V_{t=1}.

$$i = \frac{V_{t=1}}{\frac{H_0}{M_0} \times \left(\frac{1 - e^{-k}}{k}\right)} \quad (8)$$

$$k = -\ln \left(\frac{H_1 \times M_0}{H_0 \times M_1} \right) \quad (9)$$

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2.3 Carbon use efficiency

Incubations

The carbon use efficiency of soil microbes is measured (Spohn et al., 2016) using a novel substrate-independent method based on incorporation of ^{18}O from labeled water into microbial DNA with concurrent measurements of basal respiration. Microbial CUE is determined in four replicates based on incorporation of ^{18}O into microbial DNA. For this purpose, eight replicates of 200 mg of pre-incubated soil were weighed into 2 ml screw cap vials. One half of them was labelled with ^{18}O - H_2O (97.0 at%, Campro Scientific) with a syringe to reach 20.0 at% of ^{18}O in the final soil water. The other half was amended with the same volume of non-labelled Millipore water to serve as natural abundance controls. After water addition, the soil water potential of soil is -100kPa. The vials are incubated for 24 h at 15°C before they are transferred in liquid N_2 to freeze the soils. To estimate the respiration activity of soil microbes, another set of four replicates of 15 g of fresh soil is incubated in flasks of 100 ml for 24 h at 15°C . The flasks are flushed with CO_2 -free air at the beginning of incubation. The CO_2 concentration in gas sample after incubation is determined by gas chromatography (Gas Chromatograph Clarus 480, PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA).

DNA extraction and analysis

DNA is extracted from the entire soil sample of the labeled and the non-labeled soil using a DNA extraction kit (DNeasy PowerSoil Kit; Qiagen). The weight of the DNA extract is determined, and the DNA concentration in each extract is determined fluorimetrically on a 5 mL aliquot by the picogreen assay (Sandaa et al., 1998) using a kit (Quant-iT™ PicoGreen® dsDNA Reagent, Life Technologies). The 35ug of the DNA extract is dried in a silver capsule at 60°C over night to remove any water, together with 200ug of salmon DNA to ensure enough levels of oxygen in the further measurements. Subsequently, the ^{18}O abundance and the total O content are measured using a Thermochemical elemental analyzer (TC/EA Thermo Fisher) coupled via a Conflo III open split system (Thermo Fisher) to an Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (Delta V Advantage, Thermo Fisher).

Calculations

The respiration flux is calculated based on the amount of CO_2eC produced during the incubation and the duration of the incubation period. The amount of DNA produced during the incubation is calculated for each labelled sample based on the abundance of ^{18}O in (i) the labelled DNA, (ii) the non-labelled DNA (natural abundance), and (iii) the soil water of the labelled sample. Using a linear regression between the concentration of DNA in soil and the concentration of soil MBC, the amount of DNA produced during the incubation is transformed into the amount of MBC produced. The flux of C allocated to biomass production is calculated by dividing the amount of MBC produced during the incubation by the duration of the incubation.

Based on the steady-state assumption, the amount of C taken up by the microbial biomass (C_{Uptake}) was calculated as

$$C_{\text{Uptake}} = C_{\text{Growth}} + C_{\text{Respiration}}$$

where C_{Growth} is the flux of C allocated to biomass production (growth), and $C_{\text{Respiration}}$ is the flux of C allocated to the production of CO_2 (respiration).

Microbial CUE was then calculated by the following equation

$$\text{CUE} = C_{\text{Growth}} / (C_{\text{Growth}} + C_{\text{Respiration}})$$

Spohn, M., Pötsch, E.M., Eichorst, S.A., Woebken, D., Wanek, W., Richter, A., 2016. Soil microbial carbon use efficiency and biomass turnover in a long-term fertilization experiment in a temperate grassland. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 97, 168–175. doi:10.1016/j.soilbio.2016.03.008

Labelling with $^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ and soil samples for biomarker analysis

Preparation of the material

Prepare 1 M NaOH solution by adding 40 g (=1 M) NaOH in a flask and water until 1 L is reached (scale it up if more is needed). Add a magnet in the flask and place it on a magnetic stirrer until all the NaOH is dissolved.

Add 50 g of ^{13}C -bicarbonate to a flask and the 1M NaOH solution until 1 L is reached (to reach approximate saturation). Add a magnet in the flask and place it on a magnetic stirrer until all the NaOH is dissolved.

Labelling in the field

PVC cylinders (e.g., 30 cm diameter and 25 cm depth) or frames should be inserted in the field at least one week prior the start of labelling.

50 ml Eppendorf tubes are attached to plastic sticks, which are placed one in each plot/cylinder.

The desired amount of ^{13}C -sodium bicarbonate solution is added to each tube (for cover crops, 5-10 ml). Cylinders are enclosed in transparent plastic bags, sealed with rubber bands at the base of the cylinder.

The same amount of 2 M HCl is added with a syringe through the bag in order to liberate ^{13}C labelled CO_2 . The hole is closed with adhesive tape.

Bags are removed after one-three hours; the 50 ml tubes are removed, emptied in a container and washed.

Based on the aim of the labelling, this can be done once (pulse labeling) or multiple times (multiple pulse). For multiple pulse labelling of cover crops, 2/week during the entire growing period is recommended.

Contact Jim Rasmussen (AU-AGRO, jim.rasmussen@agro.au.dk) for the detailed *in situ* $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ -labeling protocol and see the procedure at following link: [In situ isotopic labeling of cover crops with \$^{13}\text{C-CO}_2\$](#)

Upon sampling the ^{13}C -labeled plant and soil, the phyllo- and rhizodeposition is estimated based on bulk ^{13}C analysis. For the present purpose a further subsample of topsoil shall be obtained for biomarker-isotope analysis (PLFA-SIP and AS-SIP) (Peixoto et al., 2020 – section 2.7). The topsoil subsample (approximately 100 g wet weight is sufficient) shall be frozen and freeze dried onsite (if possible), and then send to AU-AGRO for biomarker-analysis (send to: Jim Rasmussen, Department of Agroecology, Blichers Alle 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark).

Reference

Peixoto L., Elsgaard L., Rasmussen J., Kuzyakov Y., Banfield C., Dippold M.A., Olesen J.E. (2020) Decreased rhizodepositon, but increased microbial carbon stabilization with soil depth down to 3.6 m. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 150, 108008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2020.108008>

WP6

SOIL C RETAINMENT THROUGH STABLE AGGREGATES AND MICROBIAL BIOMASS ACTIVITY

Objective

Evaluation of the impact of agricultural practices on chemical and physical stabilization of soil organic matter and microbial activity during the stationary and active growth phases in order to identify the relevant indicators for modelling of soil C dynamic

T6.1: Physical stabilization of organic soil C pools and aggregate stability

Skaidre Suproniene - LAMMC, Alessandra Trinchera - CREA

Distribution and stability of water-stable aggregates (WSAs)

The soil samples will be collected only at MAX plant uptake, following the sampling plan (3 treatments x 4 blocks). Only at CREA, LAMMC and INIA-CSIC, on two treatments 12 additional soil samples will be collected in each site, maintaining three separated replicates/block.

Soil sampling and preparation for the aggregate stability analysis:

- the sampling should be done when soil is of **adequate moisture** (normally moist – moisture close to field capacity) **at sampling**. If soil is too wet or too dry, the soil structure can be damaged, and it would influence the results of the analysis.
- soil sample of 0-20 cm in depth at approximately 5 cm thick is taken from the carefully diged hole by a flat shovel (fig. 1). Number of samples depends on the “AGROECOseqC sampling plan”. One hole – one sample, do not dig any sub-samples and don’t mix the soil from separate sub-samples.
- cut the additional soil, using the knife, in order to have a sample of 0-20 cm length and about 15 cm wide (fig. 1)
- gently broke, the soil to approximately one-centimetre clumps in diameter (it is important to break the larger clumps before drying) (fig. 2) <https://youtu.be/EUnoaGxVmsY>

- remove the impurities (stones, larger plant residues, etc.) (fig. 2)
- place the prepared sample to the plastic or other rigid box and air dry naturally at room temperature (fig. 2)
- depending on soil texture and moisture, the samples should be air dried for approximately 1 month before shipping to LAMMC (fig. 2)

Fig. 1 Collecting of the soil sample

Fig. 2 Soil sample preparation.

Hereafter, the video showing the soil sampling mode for soil aggregates analysis:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cH7F_ERTWRs&list=PL1yv6K32UWo_CFMAQfu6VzE5gjq-3Y-za

Required quantity of the prepared air-dried soil sample, for the analysis procedure is **approximately 1 – 1.5 kg, but not lower than 900 g.**

The samples must be transported in a steady plastic or other kind of boxes or containers with lids (for example for food storage). The samples should be protected against compression and stay steady (no moving in the shipping box) during transportation in order not to damage the soil structure. For this purpose, air bubble films, air bags (Fig. 3) or other material can be used.

Fig. 3 Protection of the soil sample during transportation.

Contact details and address for sample delivery:

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Lithuania

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Analysis procedure for the soil aggregate stability

Dry sieving process:

- 1) 3 dry soil samples x 200g each is weighted.
- 2) Sieving procedure by Retsch sieve shaker: mesh sizes 8, 5.6, 4, 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25 mm.
- 3) Shaking amplitude 60, sieving time 2min.
- 4) The soil left on each sieve is weighted. Soil from the 1 mm sieve (from 2 separate sieving's) is analysed for the wet sieving procedure, the aggregates from 3rd sieving will be used to maintain the SOC, WEOC and C-stocks concentrations analysis with fine macro-aggregates (0.25-1.0 mm fractions: from 0.5 and 0.25 mm sieves) and coarse macro-aggregates (>1.0 mm (4-1 mm) fractions: from 2 and 1 mm sieves).
- 5) The min. sample size for aggregate stability test is 8g, but preferably to have about 20g (in case of difference between 2 laboratory replicates is too high and the test should be repeated). If the obtained amount of needed fraction is not sufficient for the wet sieving procedure as well as for the the SOC, WEOC and C-stocks concentrations analysis, the dry sieving procedure (1–3) has to be repeated (therefore 900 g as the minimum quantity of the sample was indicated).

Wet sieving procedure by Ejkelkamp apparatus:

- 1) Two laboratory replicates at 4 g of each 1–2 mm soil fraction (from 1 mm sieve) sample is weighed, placed on a numbered 0.25 mm sieves (arranged in the numbered cylinders), moisten with distilled water by hand fog-sprayer (by 20 times push) and wait for about 15 min until samples get wet. After 15 min. the samples with sieves are placed in the apparatus, with numbered holes and the cylinder placed below the sieves according to numbers.
- 2) 100 ml of distilled water is added to each cylinder, the sieves with samples immersed down to the cylinders with distilled water and the apparatus turned on for the 3 min. up and down sieving procedure. Non stable aggregates are separated by this procedure and remains in the cylinders with distilled water. The sieves with water stable soil aggregates, placed on side on the top of the apparatus hole and allowed to drain. After that the cylinders removed
- 3) For separation of water stable aggregates: prepare an alkalic solution of 2 g sodium hexametaphosphate ($(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$) / 1 L distilled water. New numbered cylinders filled with prepared solution and placed below the sieves according to the above mentioned procedure and continuing the sieving process for about 0.5 – 3 hours (depending on soil type). The sieving procedure lasts as long as there is no soil left, only garbage and pebbles remain.
- 4) After the sieving all the cylinders are oven-dried at 110°C for about 17–24 h (including an extra sample for control of 100ml alkalic solution without the soil).

Before weighing, the cylinders are placed in an exicator or left in an oven to cool down.

Calculations:

WSA- water stable aggregates

NSA – non-stable aggregates

AC – alkalic control

WSA % = (WSA g – AC g) / (NSA g + WSA g – AC g) 100%.

References

Velykis, A., Satkus, A., 2018. The impact of tillage, Ca-amendent and cover crop on the physical state of clay loam soil. *Zemdirbyste-Agriculture*, 105, 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.13080/z-a.2018.105.001>.

SOC, WEOC and C-stocks concentrations: Evaluate the impact of agricultural practices and soil management on SOC, water extractable C (WEOC) and C-stocks in fine macro-aggregates (0.25-1.0 mm) and coarse macro-aggregates (>1.0 mm) of soil.

Chemical determination on soil samples,

Available phosphorus (P₂O₅)

Country	Method	Description of extraction
Germany, Austria...	Calcium-Acetate-Lactate (CAL)	A solution of calcium lactate , calcium acetate , acetic acid and water , buffered to pH 3.7 to 4.1 , is used as the extraction agent. In preparation, the floors are air-dried and sieved. A suitable measuring method is photometry , for phosphorus spectrophotometric measurement of the deep blue antimony-phosphorus molybdate complex.
Slovakia, Čekija, Italy, ..	Mehlich III (ME-3)	Mehlich-3 method where solution of 0.2 M acetic acid + 0.015 M ammonium fluoride + 0.013 M nitric acid + 0.25 M ammonium nitrate + 0.001M EDTA is used as an extracting agent.
Latvia, Poland...	Egner-Riehm (D-L)	Egner-Riehm method (LV ST ZM 82-97), where 0.04 M calcium lactate extraction is used as an extracting agent acidified by hydrochloric acid up to pH 3.5 – 3.7
Lithuania, Hungary, Slovenia...	Egner-Riehm-Domingo (A-L)	0.1N ammonium lactate in 0.4N CH ₃ COOH, pH 3.7
Widely applied	Olsen	Olsen method (LVS ISO 11263:2002) – extracting agent 0.5 M sodium hydrocarbonate solution, its reaction with sodium hydroxide reaches the precision of pH 8.5 . Note: the pH of the soil affects the amount of P extracted by the Olsen method. High pH soils give lower Olsen P levels, whereas low pH soils will yield higher Olsen P

		levels, often over-estimating the soil P status.
	Bray-1 extractant	The soil phosphorus measured is that which is extracted by a solution consisting of 0.025 normal HCl and 0.03 normal NH ₄ F, referred to as Bray-1 extractant.
Sometimes applied USA...	Bray-2 extractant	The Bray 2 extractant (Bray and Kurtz, 1945) (0.03 M NH ₄ F and 0.1 M HCl) was used in a 2.5 cm ³ soil/16 mL extractant ratio.
Sometimes applied USA...	Water extractable P	Water-extractable P is determining with deionized water using a 4 cm ³ soil/50 mL extractant ratio (Korndorfer et al., 1995)

P content in all collected extracts is analyzed by using simultaneous plasma emission spectrophotometer (ICP-OES, $\lambda = 720 \text{ nm}$).

Total nitrogen (in plant and soil)

Kjeldahl nitrogen

Total Phosphorus (in plant and soil after wet digestion)

Spectrophotometrically

Ammonia

Proposed method 1: Determination of exchangeable nitrogen, as the sum of soluble inorganic nitrogen fractions (nitric and nitrous) and ammoniacal nitrogen bound to the exchange sites of soil colloids, is based on stirring the soil sample, sieved at 2mm, with a solution of potassium chloride (1M) in the ratio 5 g dry soil equivalent/40ml KCl 2 M for half an hour. The extract is obtained by settling the suspension and then centrifuging. Under these conditions the potassium ion exchanges the ammonia ion bound to the exchange sites, which is therefore put into solution, while the soluble fraction comprising nitrates and nitrites is dissolved and extracted by the dipolar effect of water (Bremner, 1965; Italian Gazette n. 248 of 21/10/1999 "Official Methods for Soil Chemical Analysis" - Method 19, 1999).

Proposed method 2: A Study of a Determination of Ammonia: Modified Berthelot Reaction Using Salicylate and Dichloroisocyanurate. Michael O. Krom, 1980.

Semi-quantitative micro-analysis in soil fine and coarse macro-aggregates by Electron Dispersive Spectroscopy

Objective:

Evaluate the impact of agricultural practices and soil management on C/P ratio in soil fine and **coarse** macro-aggregates (action coupled with Task 2.2).

Semiquantitative micro-analysis of soil aggregates

On soil samples prepared by LAMMC (collected at 0-20 cm in the same quadrat of phytosociological survey and plant root sampling), CREA will evaluate the C/P ratio using SEM-EDS technique.

After receiving the soil aggregates already separated by LLAMC, fine macroaggregates (0.25-1.0 mm) and coarse macroaggregates (>1 mm) will be analyzed by applying a semi-quantitative elemental analysis using an Electron Scanning Microscopy coupled with a Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy. This technique allows to describe the elemental composition of a given object surface (30 μm x 30 μm) based on the different electron back-scattering ability by different elemental nuclei, when excited by a tungsten or LaB6 electron source.

T6.2: Microbial C-respiration dynamic and mitigation of greenhouse gas emission

Leader Flavio Fornasier - CREA-VE, *co-leader*: Jim Rasmussen – AU

dsDNA and TGA using Robotized analytical system

Per each replicate: 30 g of fresh soil, frozen (-20°C).

Number of samples dsDNA/enz: 4/5 replicates per plot >> sample all plots.

Numbering of samples: from 1 to n plus correspondence to other numbering criteria

Fig. 1. Robotized analytical system for soil nutrients, dsDNA and enzymes analysis.

Soil respiration and enzyme analysis

Soil amount for respiration experiments: 70 g for each replicate put in the respirometer (including dsDNA/enz).

Thus considering dsDNA and enzymatic activities, per each replicate, we suggest to send 100g of frozen, fresh soil, to be sent to CREA VE under dry ice or frozen at -20°C.

- CO_2 and N_2O evolution is determined by an automated system for continuous gas sampling and analysis.
- The system operates as an “open chamber” system in which the sealed plastic jars containing the soil sample are continuously aerated at constant flow rate (15 ml min^{-1}).
- By means of valves the output of a selected jar is cyclically directed to a GC chromatograph (Agilent 7890A) for GHG content measurement.

- The system can operate automatically with up to 30 samples and allows the measurement of the evolution rate of greenhouse gases over regular periods

Example of respiration curves:

